

A PREGNANT WOMAN WITH FLAWLESS SHAPED STELLATE CATARACT

Ömer EKİCİ¹

¹World Eye Hospital - Konya

ABSTRACT

Traumatic cataracts can develop following either penetrating or blunt ocular trauma. Cataracts can form rapidly or gradually following blunt trauma. One of the clinical presentations of blunt traumatic cataracts can be also star (stellate) or rosette-shaped appearance. Stellate cataract is uncommon. In this case, a 32-year-old pregnant patient, who was diagnosed with an almost perfect star-shaped stellate cataract due to the complaint of low vision that started after blunt trauma in the right eye, was presented.

Keywords: Blunt trauma, Pregnancy, Subcapsular opacification, Star shaped cataract,

KUSURSUZ ŐEKİLLİ YILDIZ KATARAKTI OLAN HAMİLE BİR KADIN

Ömer EKİCİ¹

¹Dünya Göz Hastanesi - Konya

ÖZET

Delici veya künt göz travmaları sonrasında travmatik katarakt görülebilir. Katarakt künt travmadan hemen sonra veya geç dönemde ortaya çıkabilir. Künt travma sonrası görülen kataraktların klinik belirtilerinden biri de yıldız (stellate) veya rozet şeklinde görülen lens opasitesidir. Satellit katarakt nadir görülür. Bu olguda, sağ gözde künt travma sonrası başlayan görme azlığı şikayeti nedeniyle kusursuza yakın yıldız şeklinde katarakt tanısı konulan 32 yaşında hamile bir hasta sunuldu.

Anahtar kelimeler: Gebelik, Künt travma, Subkapsüler opasifikasyon, Yıldız şekilli katarakt

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INTRODUCTION

Ocular trauma plays a crucial role in contributing to visual impairment, primarily linked to traumatic cataracts(1). Penetrating injury, blunt injury, electric shock, radiation exposure, ultraviolet (UV) light exposure and chemical damage can affect the crystalline lens in multiple ways.(2,3). Lens opacification can manifest either immediately following an injury or develop over the course of years(4). Cataracts that result from blunt trauma often display a characteristic stellate or rosette shaped appearance(5).

CASE REPORT

A 32-year-old pregnant woman applied to our clinic with low vision in her right eye. She was 29-weeks pregnant. 3 months ago, while she was sleeping, her 2-year-old child's heel hit her right eye hard. She did not receive any medical help and her vision in her right eye decreased over time.

Best corrected visual acuity (BCVA) was 0.3 with +6.00-2.00x175 in the right eye and 0.6 with +9.00-2.00x180 in the left eye. The results of the biomicroscopic examination showed an anterior subcapsular stellate cataract at the center of the lens in the right eye (Figure 1a, Figure 1b). The lens was clear in the left eye. The anterior lens capsule was intact in the right eye, and no additional examination findings indicative of trauma such as phacodonesis or iridodonesis were found. No pathological findings were observed in the fundus examination in both eyes. Axial length 21.63 mm on the right, 21.37 mm on the left; anterior chamber depth was 3.51 mm on the right and 3.40 mm on the left. Central corneal thickness was 601 µm in the right eye and 602 µm in the left eye (Figure 2). On detailed questioning, there was no history of electric shock, drug use, smoking, UV or ionising radiation exposure that she could remember in her lifetime. She had no history of systemic disease.

Since the patient was 29 weeks pregnant, surgery was recommended after birth. However, the patient stated that her current low vision was extremely disturbing and that she wanted to have surgery as soon as possible. After consultations regarding the fetus, cataract surgery was planned. Phacoemulsification surgery was performed on the right eye under topical anesthesia. There were no problems with the mother and fetus during and after the surgery.. No pathological conditions were encountered, especially in terms of the anterior capsule, posterior capsule and lens zonules. A monofocal toric intraocular lens was implanted.

On the first postoperative day examination, intraocular lens was centralized (Figure 3) and BCVA was 0.7 with +0,50-0.75x180. It was thought that there might be refractive amblyopia because the axial lengths in both eyes were below 22 mm. Topical levofloxacin was used 4 times a day for 2 weeks and topical dexamethasone was used 4 times a day for 1 month postoperatively. She was told to apply punctal compression for 2 minutes after instilling the drops to reduce the transfer of drugs into the systemic circulation.

The patient mentioned in the study provided informed consent, and all procedures were conducted in adherence to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki.

Figure 1a. The slit lamp examination of the anterior subcapsular stellate cataract

Figure 1b. Slit lamp examination under retroillumination of the stellate cataract.

OD right		IOL calculation		OS left	
●		●		●	
Eye status					
LS: Phakic	VS: Vitreous body	LS: Phakic	VS: Vitreous body	LS: Phakic	VS: Vitreous body
Ref: ---	VA: ---	Ref: ---	VA: ---	Ref: ---	VA: ---
LVC: Untreated	LVC mode: -	LVC: Untreated	LVC mode: -	LVC: Untreated	LVC mode: -
Target ref: plano	SIA: +0.25 D @ 0°	Target ref: plano	SIA: +0.25 D @ 0°	Target ref: plano	SIA: +0.25 D @ 0°
Biometric values					
AL 21.63 mm (I)	SD 22 µm	AL 21.37 mm	SD 6 µm	AL 21.37 mm	SD 6 µm
ACD 3.51 mm	SD 6 µm	ACD 3.40 mm	SD 6 µm	ACD 3.40 mm	SD 6 µm
LT 3.65 mm	SD 38 µm	LT 3.73 mm	SD 9 µm	LT 3.73 mm	SD 9 µm
WTW 12.5 mm		WTW 12.1 mm		WTW 12.1 mm	
SE 41.73 D	SD 0.01 D	SE 41.30 D	SD 0.01 D	SE 41.30 D	SD 0.01 D
ΔK -2.62 D @ 178°	K1 40.46 D @ 178°	ΔK -3.33 D @ 2°	K1 39.70 D @ 2°	ΔK -3.33 D @ 2°	K1 39.70 D @ 2°
TSE 41.98 D	SD 0.04 D	TSE 41.44 D	SD 0.03 D	TSE 41.44 D	SD 0.03 D
ΔTK -2.62 D @ 177°	TK1 40.71 D @ 177°	ΔTK -3.28 D @ 2°	TK1 39.87 D @ 2°	ΔTK -3.28 D @ 2°	TK1 39.87 D @ 2°
	TK2 43.33 D @ 87°		TK2 43.15 D @ 92°		TK2 43.15 D @ 92°
Alcon SN60WF		Alcon SN60WF		Alcon SN60WF	
- SRK®/T -		- Haigis -		- SRK®/T -	
A const: 119.00		A const: 119.00		A const: 119.00	
IOL (D)	Ref (D)	IOL (D)	Ref (D)	IOL (D)	Ref (D)
+30.50	-0.84	+32.00	-0.86	+31.50	-0.58
+30.00	-0.46	+31.50	-0.49	+31.00	-0.20
+29.50	-0.09	+31.00	-0.12	+30.50	+0.17
+29.00	+0.28	+30.50	+0.24	+30.00	+0.54
+28.50	+0.64	+30.00	+0.60	+29.50	+0.91
+29.38	Emmetropia	+30.83	Emmetropia	+30.73	Emmetropia
Alcon SN60WF		Alcon SN60WF		Alcon SN60WF	
- Hoffer® Q -		- Holladay 1 -		- Hoffer® Q -	
pACD: +5.64		SF: +1.84		pACD: +5.64	
IOL (D)	Ref (D)	IOL (D)	Ref (D)	IOL (D)	Ref (D)
+32.00	-0.90	+31.00	-0.64	+33.50	-0.86
+31.50	-0.53	+30.50	-0.27	+33.00	-0.49
+31.00	-0.17	+30.00	+0.09	+32.50	-0.13
+30.50	+0.19	+29.50	+0.45	+32.00	+0.23
+30.00	+0.54	+29.00	+0.80	+31.50	+0.59
+30.76	Emmetropia	+30.12	Emmetropia	+32.32	Emmetropia
Alcon SN60WF		Alcon SN60WF		Alcon SN60WF	
- SRK®/T -		- Haigis -		- SRK®/T -	
A const: 119.00		A const: 119.00		A const: 119.00	
IOL (D)	Ref (D)	IOL (D)	Ref (D)	IOL (D)	Ref (D)
+30.50	-0.84	+32.00	-0.86	+31.50	-0.58
+30.00	-0.46	+31.50	-0.49	+31.00	-0.20
+29.50	-0.09	+31.00	-0.12	+30.50	+0.17
+29.00	+0.28	+30.50	+0.24	+30.00	+0.54
+28.50	+0.64	+30.00	+0.60	+29.50	+0.91
+29.38	Emmetropia	+30.83	Emmetropia	+30.73	Emmetropia
Alcon SN60WF		Alcon SN60WF		Alcon SN60WF	
- Hoffer® Q -		- Holladay 1 -		- Hoffer® Q -	
pACD: +5.64		SF: +1.84		pACD: +5.64	
IOL (D)	Ref (D)	IOL (D)	Ref (D)	IOL (D)	Ref (D)
+32.00	-0.90	+31.00	-0.64	+33.50	-0.86
+31.50	-0.53	+30.50	-0.27	+33.00	-0.49
+31.00	-0.17	+30.00	+0.09	+32.50	-0.13
+30.50	+0.19	+29.50	+0.45	+32.00	+0.23
+30.00	+0.54	+29.00	+0.80	+31.50	+0.59
+30.76	Emmetropia	+30.12	Emmetropia	+32.32	Emmetropia

Figure 2. Biometry reports.

Figure 3. Postoperative next day (Intraocular lens)

DISCUSSION

Ocular trauma frequently results in significant vision impairment. Each year, 55 million ocular injuries are reported, resulting in approximately 1.6 million cases of vision loss attributed to traumatic cataracts(1,3).

Traumatic cataracts can manifest through either the direct rupture and deformation of the lens capsule or through impact-induced equatorial stretching. These changes are caused by a number of factors that transmit traumatic stress energy to the contralateral part of the eye(6).

In instances of penetrating trauma, development of a traumatic cataract may occur instantly upon contact of the penetrant object with the lens(7). Blunt trauma can cause cataracts in the absence of capsular damage due to the forces exerted during the initial injury or the following inflammation(8). Electric shock can result in either diffuse milky-white opacification or the formation of multiple snowflake-like opacities. Chemical trauma can manifest when a foreign substance such as thallium, naphthalene, galactose and lactose, penetrates the eye and disrupts the structure of the lens(3,9). Exposure to ionizing radiation, often utilized in the treatment of ocular tumors or during cardiac interventions, has a potential to damage and rupture the lens. Ultraviolet radiation, on the other hand, can lead to true exfoliation of the lens capsule, subsequently resulting cataract(10,11)

Both slit lamp biomicroscopy and a dilated fundus examination are necessary and should be conducted. It is essential to identify indications of zonular defects which may encompass phacodonesis, focal iridodonesis, vitreous prolapse, and lens subluxation, although these indications are not always obvious(12). Capsular integrity, adequacy of zonule fibers,

existence of synechiae and vitreous extrusion must be considered when choosing a surgical approach(13).

The surgical intervention for traumatic cataracts demands a complex procedure, necessitating meticulous and thoughtful deliberation(11). The lens capsule and zonules are commonly susceptible to damage, leading to an increased risk of intraoperative issues, including capsular tear, intraoperative lens displacement and vitreous loss(14). The morphological characteristics of cataracts play a major part in determining the choice of surgical approach and subsequently the final visual results(7) In a study comparing patients with open and closed globe injuries who were matched for similar features, the achievement of acceptable visual acuity after traumatic cataract surgery was markedly better in cases with open injuries(15).

Educating patients on the adoption of precautionary measures to prevent eye trauma is crucial. This includes the use of protective equipments like glasses and eye shields, minimizing exposure to environments with potential risks, and avoiding potential harm from infrared or ultraviolet rays(16)

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REFERENCES

1. Khokhar S, Gupta S, Yogi R, Gogia V, Agarwal T. Epidemiology and intermediate-term outcomes of open- and closed-globe injuries in traumatic childhood cataract. *Eur J Ophthalmol.* 2014 Jan-Feb;24(1):124-30. <https://doi.org/10.5301/ejo.5000342>
2. Gupta VB, Rajagopala M, Ravishankar B. Etiopathogenesis of cataract: an appraisal. *Indian J Ophthalmol.* 2014 Feb;62(2):103-10. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0301-4738.121141>
3. Shanbagh S, Matalia J, Kannan R, Shetty R, Panmand P, Muthu SO et al. Distinct gene expression profiles underlie morphological and etiological differences in pediatric cataracts. *Indian J Ophthalmol.* 2023 May;71(5):2143-2151. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijo.ijo_3269_22
4. Tartarella MB, Britez-Colombi GF, Milhomem S, Lopes MC, Fortes Filho JB. Pediatric cataracts: clinical aspects, frequency of strabismus and chronological, etiological, and morphological features. *Arq Bras Oftalmol.* 2014 May-Jun;77(3):143-7. <https://doi.org/10.5935/0004-2749.20140037>
5. Asano N, Schlötzer-Schrehardt U, Dörfler S, Naumann GO. Ultrastructure of contusion cataract. *Arch Ophthalmol.* 1995 Feb;113(2):210-5. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archophth.1995.01100020094037>
6. Inanc M, Tekin K, Erol YO, Sargon MF, Koc M, Budakoglu O, Yılmazbas P. The ultrastructural alterations in the lens capsule and epithelium in eyes with traumatic white cataract. *Int Ophthalmol.* 2019 Jan;39(1):47-53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10792-017-0783-0>
7. Chaudhary A, Singh R, Singh SP. Prognostic value of Ocular Trauma Score and pediatric Penetrating Ocular Trauma Score in predicting the visual prognosis following ocular injury. *Rom J Ophthalmol.* 2022 Apr-Jun;66(2):146-152. <https://doi.org/10.22336/rjo.2022.29>
8. El Kaissoumi L, Mrini B. Neglected post-traumatic ruptured cataract. *Pan Afr Med J.* 2022;42:3. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2022.42.3.33130>
9. Stepp MA, Menko AS. Immune responses to injury and their links to eye disease. *Transl Res.* 2021 Oct;236:52-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trsl.2021.05.005>

10. Hilely A, Leiba H, Achiron A, Hecht I, Parness-Yossifon R. Traumatic Cataracts in Children, Long-Term Follow-up in an Israeli Population: A Retrospective Study. *Isr MedAssoc J.* 2019 Sep;21(9):599-602. [PubMed: 31542904]
11. Bendeddouche K, Assaf E, Emadisson H, Forestier F, Salvanet-Bouccara A. [Air bags and eye injuries: chemical burns and major traumatic ocular lesions--a case study]. *J FrOphthalmol.* 2003 Oct;26(8):819-23. [PubMed: 14586223]
12. Doğan E, Çelik E, Gündoğdu KÖ, Alagöz G. Characteristics of pediatric traumatic cataract and factors affecting visual outcomes. *Injury.* 2023 Jan;54(1):168-172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.injury.2022.09.034>
13. Oudjani N, Renault D, Courrier E, Malek Y. Phacoemulsification And Zonular Weakness:Contribution Of The Capsular Tension Ring With A Thread. *Clin Ophthalmol.*2019;13:2301-2304. <https://doi.org/10.2147/opth.s212063>
14. Xiong S, Xia X. Risk factors and surgical outcomes for the concurrence of intraocular lens dislocation with vitreoretinal diseases. *Zhong Nan Da Xue Xue Bao Yi Xue Ban.* 2022 Jul28;47(7):881-887. <https://doi.org/10.11817/j.issn.1672-7347.2022.220264>
15. Batchelor A, Lacy M, Hunt M, Lu R, Lee AY, Lee CS et al. IRIS Registry Analytic Center Consortium. Predictors of Long-term Ophthalmic Complications after Closed Globe Injuries Using the Intelligent Research in Sight (IRIS®) Registry. *OphthalmolSci.* 2023 Mar;3(1):100237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xops.2022.100237>
16. Guo Y, Liu Y, Xu H, Zhao Z, Gan D. Characteristics of pediatric patients hospitalised for eye trauma in 2007-2015 and factors related to their visual outcomes. *Eye (Lond).*2021Mar;35(3):945-951. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41433-020-1002-1>